

Table S4. Multivariate mixed-effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* mutations in pregnant women (recent IPTp-SP use)

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and p values are presented (p values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effects	N51				C59				S108				Triple <i>dhfr</i>			
	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>
Age (10 years)	0.30	0.12	0.75	0.010	0.47	0.17	1.28	0.139	0.48	0.17	1.35	0.166	0.38	0.19	0.80	0.010
Gravidity	0.24	0.97	1.59	0.087	1.12	0.84	1.48	0.439	1.16	0.86	1.57	0.326	1.17	0.94	1.45	0.165
Season#	1.06	0.67	1.66	0.818	1.05	0.61	1.82	0.849	1.03	0.58	1.82	0.920	1.03	0.67	1.57	0.896
Recent IPTp-SP [†]	2.16	0.83	5.65	0.116	1.76	0.52	5.96	0.362	2.73	0.63	11.79	0.178	1.71	0.73	4.01	0.219
AL	0.74	0.43	1.28	0.276	0.87	0.42	1.80	0.713	1.16	0.52	2.56	0.718	0.75	0.47	1.22	0.249
Visit*	0.19	0.03	1.23	0.081	0.24	0.03	2.33	0.219	0.20	0.02	2.38	0.201	0.18	0.03	0.97	0.045
SeasonXvisit	4.77	1.45	15.71	0.010	6.11	1.17	31.92	0.032	7.99	1.34	47.83	0.023	4.61	1.64	12.93	0.004
-Visit* in high transmission season	0.93	0.18	4.68	0.926	1.47	0.19	11.61	0.712	1.58	0.16	15.54	0.697	0.84	0.18	3.80	0.819
-Season# in Del samples	5.03	1.64	15.39	0.005	6.45	1.33	31.34	0.021	8.23	1.48	45.78	0.016	4.74	1.85	12.17	0.001
AgeXvisit	0.95	0.23	3.98	0.940	1.22	0.20	7.51	0.827	1.59	0.21	12.12	0.654	0.82	0.21	3.10	0.764
-Age in Del samples	0.29	0.08	1.10	0.068	0.58	0.11	3.07	0.518	0.77	0.12	5.040	0.786	0.31	0.10	0.96	0.042
GravidityXvisit	1.27	0.80	2.02	0.308	1.28	0.71	2.32	0.413	1.90	0.67	2.51	0.449	1.32	0.87	2.00	0.197
-Gravidity in Del samples	1.58	1.03	2.43	0.038	1.43	0.83	2.48	0.200	1.50	0.80	2.82	0.205	1.53	1.07	2.19	0.019

<i>dhps</i> Fixed effects	S436				A437			
	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>	OR	95% CI		<i>p</i>
Age (10 years)	2.52	0.80	7.97	0.115	0.71	0.29	1.70	0.440
Gravidity	0.75	0.54	1.06	0.099	1.05	0.81	1.36	0.717
Season#	1.67	0.89	3.13	0.112	0.71	0.43	1.20	0.205
Recent IPTp-SP [†]	1.07	0.40	2.87	0.892	2.54	0.68	9.44	0.166
AL	0.85	0.48	1.52	0.587	0.58	0.32	1.03	0.061
Visit*	0.26	0.03	2.46	0.239	1.44	0.19	11.12	0.725
SeasonXvisit	1.45	0.39	5.49	0.581	2.52	0.62	10.26	0.197
-Visit* in high transmission season	0.38	0.05	3.13	0.365	3.63	0.50	26.67	0.204
-Season# in Del samples	2.42	0.69	8.49	0.166	1.80	0.49	6.64	0.377
AgeXvisit	0.42	0.07	2.64	0.353	0.93	0.17	5.23	0.934
-Age in Del samples	1.05	0.25	4.49	0.945	0.66	0.15	2.91	0.581
GravidityXvisit	1.34	0.76	2.34	0.313	0.92	0.55	1.54	0.745
-Gravidity in Del samples	1.00	0.65	1.56	0.987	0.96	0.62	1.51	0.869

Del = delivery; †= IPTp-SP dose in past 30 days (0 = no, 1 = yes); #low transmission season = 0, high transmission season = 1; *ANC1 = 0, Delivery = 1; age centred at 25 years